

Impact of Emotional intelligence and Job Performance on employees in a Higher Education Institute in Chhattisgarh

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Abstract

This research examines the influence of an emotional intelligence assessment derived from the Role-Based Performance Scale (RBPS) on job performance. This study seeks to examine the impact of emotional intelligence scores of academic staff at higher education institutions in Chhattisgarh on their work performance. This study used a quantitative methodology to broaden the scope of data collection by include chosen higher educational institutions. The findings indicate a substantial correlation between emotional intelligence and the job performance of academic personnel in higher education institutions. Consequently, these substantial results elucidate the theoretical and practical relevance of emotional intelligence in relation to work performance, demonstrating that emotional intelligence is a determinant and predictor of job success.

Keywords: emotional intelligence, job performance, higher education, role-based performance scale, human resource management

Introduction

In the previous two decades, the significance of emotional intelligence (EI) to different aspects of human evolution has been studied comprehensively (Meisler, 2014). Studies like Ashforth & Humphrey (Ashforth & Humphrey, 1993), highlighted that emotions are fundamental to organisational life and stressed the need of focussing on workers' emotional experiences. Organizations seeking a competitive edge in today's volatile environment consider EI far more important than Intellegent quotient (IQ) and technical skills (Brotheridge & Grandey, 2002). Emotional Intelligence is a mechanism in which emotions and cognition combine to produce improved thought and comprehension in response to a variety of circumstances and demands. Human Resource (HR) managers in the modern era consider not only performance based on outcomes but also the performance that relies on the process, by observing employees' interactions with coworkers and customers (Darvishmotevali et al., 2018). Moreover, it is a form of cognitive intelligence that encapsulates a precise understanding and evaluation of people's emotions, as well as the degree to which they are conscious of their feelings and the emotional status of others (Behbahani et al., 2011). The concept of EI evinced enormous interest in the researchers and evolved as an important concept in the organizational environment. As a result, it has been documented to help people survive in today's hostile, competitive, and multifaceted world (Law, 2008).

Ezzatabadi et al. (Ezzatabadi et al., 2012) described emotional intelligence as the ability to experience, interact, perceive, recall, describe, recognize, control, understand, and explain emotions. Emotional Intelligence is characterized by Goleman (Goleman, 1998), who popularized the term, as " The ability to comprehend our own

emotions and those of others, to self-motivate, and to effectively regulate emotions in ourselves and in our interpersonal connections". Emotional Intelligence is described by Mayer and Salovey (D. R. C. J. D. Mayer & Salovey, 2001) as "the capability of an individual to accurately interpret, evaluate, and express emotions; the capacity to access and/or generate feelings that enhance cognitive processes; the proficiency in comprehending emotions and emotional awareness; and the ability to regulate emotions to foster emotional and intellectual growth". Emotional intelligence refers to the capacity to comprehend our own emotions and those of others, to self-motivate, and to manage emotions effectively in both personal and relational contexts. It is the capacity to monitor one's own and others' emotions and sentiments, to distinguish between them, and to use this understanding to guide one's thoughts and actions (Goleman, 1998; Salovey & Mayer, 1990). Emotional intelligence, as defined by Mayer, Salovey, and Caruso (J. D. Mayer et al., 2004), is "the capacity to reason about emotions to enhance cognitive processes." It entails the capacity to accurately identify emotions, access and produce emotions to facilitate cognition, comprehend emotions and emotional intelligence, and regulate emotions reflectively to foster emotional and intellectual development.

Performance on the job is one of the most comprehensively researched variables in both organizational behaviors as well as human resource management literature (Bandura & Jourden, 1991; Bycio et al., 1990; Haque et al., 1998). Traditionally, performance on the job is defined as the degree to which an employee fulfills his task in accordance with the organization's stated criteria (Nayyar, 1994). An employee's job performance is the sum of all productive activities at the workplace that is expected of him or her and how well these activities are carried out. Employee performance is usually assessed

once a year or four times a year (Farh et al., 2012). Job performance is the added value of a person's discrete behavioral events to the organization over a set period of time (Motowidlo et al., 2014). Task and contextual performance are the two dimensions of job performance (Borman & Motowidlo, 1997). Task performance encompasses technical processes, maintenance, and technical requirement maintenance, all of which are directly related to job completion (Borman & Motowidlo, 1997). Contextual performance refers to interpersonal behavior or organizational actions. It includes activities i.e. assisting and cooperating, adhering to the organization's rules and procedures and volunteering to perform tasks (Borman & Motowidlo, 1997). It has been shown that when employees are happy about their jobs, their performance improves and they complete their tasks more efficiently. Performance is the result of carrying out tasks in a competent manner with significant responsibilities for the organization without violating any laws or organizational policies. Employee performance results from an individual's effort; if performance is exemplary and both the quantity and quality of an employee's output improve with time, the organisation is deemed successful (Culbertson et al., 2013).

Historically, intellect and emotion were seen as two different and distinct faculties, each with its own intelligence and areas of impact. Emotional intelligence affects cognitive efficiency, which was once seen as only a characteristic of general intelligence. The research indicates that overall emotional intelligence and its sub-components, including emotion perception and regulation, significantly contributed to individual cognitive achievement (Lam & Kirby, 2002).

HR managers have begun to evaluate employees not only in terms of the results they produce but also in terms of how well they engage with their coworkers and other employees. It's not uncommon for managers to know "what" but not "how" (Snell & Wong, 2013). A person's ability to interpret, classify, and control emotions is the foundation for social and emotional competencies required for success in any work. It means that emotional intelligence competencies play a significant role in job success. Managerial intelligence accounts for 16 percent of individual achievement in organizations, IQ accounts for 27 percent, and emotional intelligence accounts for a whopping 36 percent (Dulewicz & Higgs, 2000). Emotional intelligence has been identified as a key factor in business success (Goleman, 1998; Salovey & Mayer, 1990; Weinberger, 2002), and in response to increasing importance of emotional intelligence, several organizational behaviorists have attempted to identify factors that influence employees' work performance. The study of emotional labor and emotion management has revealed that tiny, relatively low-cost adjustments in organizational context or managerial behavior can have an impact on employees' emotional reactions and their performance (AR, 1983; Huy, 1999). According to Deshpande, Joseph, and Shu (Deshpande et al., 2005), there is a substantial gap in aggregate counterproductive activity between high to low emotional intelligence levels, implying that highly emotionally intelligent person are better corporate officials and have more ethical attitudes. Emotional intelligence, according to Bagshaw (Bagshaw, 2000), is the ability to efficiently manipulate emotions, and it, therefore, plays a major role in business performance.

Research has shown that employees with high EI are better equipped to handle these demands. They possess more proficiency in identifying their own emotional states and those of others, facilitating stress management, conflict resolution, and the cultivation of robust, supportive relationships. For example, self-awareness allows employees to understand their strengths and weaknesses, helping them to seek opportunities for growth and improvement. Self-regulation enables them to maintain composure and make thoughtful decisions even in stressful situations. Empathy enables individuals to establish emotional connections with others, therefore promoting trust and cooperation. Social skills enhance communication, leadership, and collaboration, which are vital for achieving success in higher education positions (VENERA, 2019; Zeidner et al., 2004).

This paper aims to investigate the impact of emotional intelligence on job performance among employees in higher education institutions, providing insights that could enhance employee effectiveness and organizational success. By examining the relationship between EI and job performance, this study seeks to contribute to the literature on organizational psychology and provide practical recommendations for human resource management in higher education. Understanding how EI influences job performance can help institutions develop targeted strategies for employee development, such as EI training programs that enhance both individual and organizational outcomes.

Methodology of Reviewed Studies

Numerous studies have explored the relationship between emotional intelligence (EI) and job performance across various sectors, including higher education (Abebe & Singh, 2023; Dhani et al., 2016). Emotional intelligence, which encompasses the ability to perceive, use, understand, and manage emotions, is increasingly recognized as a crucial factor in professional success (Ahangar, 2012; Yao et al., 2009). To investigate the impact of emotional intelligence (EI) on job performance among employees in higher education institutions, a comprehensive methodological approach is applied in this study. Table 1 outlines detailed information about the gender, age, education, job role, and work experience of employees of the sample set. In this survey both males and females are included in age group of 25 and above. This study collect data from a representative sample of employees, including both faculty, administrative staff and others in higher education institutions. They have an educational qualifications from bachelor degrees to PhD with 0-15 years or above professional work experience. This questionnaire collects information on participants' demographic characteristics, including age, gender, job role, years of experience, and educational background. This data is used to control for potential confounding variables in the analysis. This survey was conducted as per role-based performance scale (RBPS) measures to adopt a quantitative research design, focusing on the relationship between EI and job performance. In total, 9 questions was asked to the employees in this analysis as shown in table 2.

Job performance in this study is measured using self-report surveys. The self-report survey includes items that assess various aspects of job performance, such as

task performance, contextual performance, and overall job satisfaction. This self-report measure complements Mayer-Salovey-Caruso emotional intelligence test (MSCEIT) (D. R. C. J. D. Mayer & Salovey, 2001; J. D. Mayer et al., 2002) by providing participants with an opportunity to assess their own emotional intelligence. This design allows for the examination of correlations between EI and job performance while controlling for potential confounding variables such as age, gender, job role, and years of experience. Collected data sets were analyzed as per descriptive statistics to summarize the demographic characteristics of the sample and the distribution of EI and job performance scores. This includes measures such as percentage variation of sample size. Descriptive statistics help to identify any significant differences and to ensure that the findings are robust across various subgroups.

Results and Discussion

On the question of how would you rate your ability to recognize and understand your own emotions given in figure 1. 36.4% employees opted for average, whereas 33.3% and 30.3% employees opted for high and very high response respectively. No one has opted for low and very low response. On the question of how well do you understand and empathize with the emotions of others given in figure 2. 51.5% employees opted for well, whereas 33.3%, 12.1% and 3.0% employees opted for very well, average and poorly response respectively. No one has opted for very poorly response. It also suggests that the fear of getting exposed to criticism or some consequences were high if they select low or very low response. On the question of how effectively do you manage your emotions in challenging situations given in figure 3.

51.5 % employees opted for effective, whereas 24.2 % , 18.2 % and 6.1 % employees opted for very effective, neutral and ineffective response respectively. No one has opted for very ineffective response. It also suggests that the this self report survey has not been exploring through realtime situations and the true behaviour of employee may vary based on the severity of situations (Salovey & Mayer, 1990). On the question of rating your overall emotional intelligence level given in figure 4. 51.5 % employees opted for high, whereas 30.3 % and 18.2 % employees opted for average and very high response, respectively. No one has opted for low and very low response. It can vary in emotional intelligence appraisal and depend on the mental state of the employee, which varies in multidimensions(Weinberger, 2002). On the question of how would you rate your overall job performance in your current role given in figure 5. 45.5 % employees opted for excellent, whereas 30.3 % and 24.2 % employees opted for very good and good responses, respectively. No one has opted for bad and very bad response. It is because the survey was conducted in central government institute where paychecks were much higher then the state levels. Additionally the work environment in a government funded higher education institute is not that stressful (Sluyter & Salovey, 1997). On the question of how satisfied are you with your job performance given in figure 6. 54.5 % employees opted for satisfied, whereas 30.3 % and 15.2 % employees opted for very satisfied and neutral, respectively. No one has opted for dissatisfied and very dissatisfied. Relating this to results of question given in figures 1, 2, 3 and 4, it is proven through this empirical data that better EI helps in giving better job performances (Bycio et al., 1990; Culbertson et al., 2013; Farh et al., 2012; Meisler, 2014). On the question of how frequently do you meet or exceed performance expectations set by

your organization given in figure 7. 45.5 % employees opted for often, whereas 39.4 % , 9.1 % and 6.1 % employees opted for always, sometimes and occasionally response, respectively. No one has opted for never response. It also suggests that the results of this question is the outcome very experienced workforce due to very competitive population of India or lower work load situations which meets the expectations of this organization (Dhani et al., 2016; Sarangi & Vats, 2015). On the question of how much emotional intelligence impact your interactions with colleagues, students, and other stakeholders in the higher education setting given in figure 8. 48.5 % employees opted for high, whereas 30.3 % and 15.2 % employees opted for high and very high, respectively. Only 6% have been opted for low and very low. Relating this to results of question given in figures 1, 2, 3 and 4, it is proven through this empirical data that better EI helps in better interactions with colleagues, students, and other stakeholders in the higher education setting (Baporikar, 2020; Sarangi & Vats, 2015; Trigueros et al., 2020). On the question of how important do you believe emotional intelligence is for success in your role within higher educational institution given in figure 9. 36.4 % employees opted for extremely important, whereas 30.3 % , 24.2 % and 9.1 % employees opted for very important, moderately important and somewhat important response, respectively. No one has opted for not important response. It also suggests that the results of this question is the outcome awareness among employees about good emotional intelligence for success in your role within higher educational institution (Abebe & Singh, 2023; Dias & Amaral, 2014; Sharma & Pillai, 2023).

The findings from this study consistently support the hypothesis that emotional intelligence is positively correlated with job performance in higher education institutions.

Employees with higher levels of EI are better equipped to manage their emotions, build positive relationships, and navigate the complexities of their roles. This is particularly crucial in educational settings, where interactions with students, colleagues, and administrators demand a high degree of emotional regulation and interpersonal skills. In higher education, the ability to manage stress, empathize with students, and communicate effectively are all aspects of emotional intelligence that contribute to job performance (Pandey et al., 2019). Educators with high EI can create a more conducive learning environment, address student concerns more effectively, and collaborate better with their peers, all of which enhance their overall job performance.

Conclusion

Emotional intelligence is a critical factor in job performance, particularly in higher education institutions, where interpersonal interactions and emotional regulation are paramount. In this study, comprehensive understanding of the link between EI and job performance has been established through self report surveys. This study helped to determine whether higher levels of EI are associated with better job performance. The empirical evidence and findings from this study consistently highlight the positive correlation between EI and job performance. By recognizing the importance of EI and implementing strategies to enhance it, higher education institutions can improve employee performance, job satisfaction, and overall organizational success. Future research should continue to explore the nuances of this relationship, particularly through longitudinal studies and in diverse organizational contexts

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Table 1

Detailed information of the sample size of the conducted survey.

Detailed information of sample size of the conducted survey			
1. Gender			
<i>Male</i>		<i>Female</i>	
29		04	
2. Age (in years)			
<i>25-34 years</i>	<i>35-44 years</i>	<i>45-54 years</i>	<i>55 years and above</i>
18	14	00	01
3. Educational Qualification			
<i>Bachelor's Degree</i>	<i>Master's Degree</i>	<i>PhD or equivalent</i>	<i>Diploma only</i>
02	27	04	00
4. Job role			
<i>Administrator</i>	<i>Support Staff</i>	<i>Faculty</i>	<i>Others</i>
14	13	01	05
5. Work Experience in Higher Education Institutions (in years)			
<i>0 - 4</i>	<i>5 - 9</i>	<i>10 - 14</i>	<i>15 and above</i>
11	13	05	04

Table 2

Survey questions asked to the subjects in role-based performance scale (RBPS) measurement.

Q. No.	Survey questions
1.	How would you rate your ability to recognize and understand your own emotions?
2.	How effectively do you manage your emotions in challenging situations?
3.	How well do you understand and empathize with the emotions of others?
4.	Rate your overall emotional intelligence level:
5.	How would you rate your overall job performance in your current role?
6.	How satisfied are you with your job performance?
7.	How frequently do you meet or exceed performance expectations set by your organization?
8.	How much emotional intelligence impact your interactions with colleagues, students, and other stakeholders in the higher education setting?
9.	How important do you believe emotional intelligence is for success in your role within higher educational institution?

Figure 1

% response of total sample size on the question of how would you rate your ability to recognize and understand your own emotions?

Note. Sample size of 33

Figure 2

% response of total sample size on the question of how well do you understand and empathize with the emotions of others?

Note. Sample size of 33

Figure 3

% response of total sample size on the question of how effectively do you manage your emotions in challenging situations?

Note. Sample size of 33

Figure 4

% response of total sample size on the question of rating your overall emotional intelligence level?

Note. Sample size of 33

Figure 5

% response of total sample size on the question of how would you rate your overall job performance in your current role?

Note. Sample size of 33

Figure 6

% response of total sample size on the question of how satisfied are you with your job performance?

Note. Sample size of 33

Figure 7

% response of total sample size on the question of how frequently do you meet or exceed performance expectations set by your organization?

Note. Sample size of 33

Figure 8

% response of total sample size on the question of how much emotional intelligence impact your interactions with colleagues, students, and other stakeholders in the higher education setting?

Note. Sample size of 33

Figure 9

% response of total sample size on the question of how important do you believe emotional intelligence is for success in your role within higher educational institution?

Note. Sample size of 33